

SIGNIFICANCE OF PRONUNCIATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE COMMUNICATION

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Annotation

An essential part of learning English is correct pronunciation. If the learner's pronunciation is poor, it causes them not to be understood by others even though their grammar, listening, writing and reading skills are perfect. Pronunciation is not only about being understood but also it gives the first initial impression of an individual. It is the physical skill that learners should practice every time. So that, instructions and practice are needed in class. This article analyses the importance of pronunciation, discusses English pronunciation and communication.

Key words: Pronunciation, English pronunciation, communication, importance of pronunciation, reason for incorrect pronunciation.

Annotatsiya

Ingliz tilini o'rganishning muhim qismi to'g'ri talaffuzdir. Agar o'quvchining talaffuzi yomon bo'lsa, bu ularning grammatika, tinglash, yozish va o'qish qobiliyatlari mukammal bo'lsa ham, boshqalar tomonidan tushunilmasligiga olib keladi. Talaffuz nafaqat tushunish, balki shaxs haqida dastlabki taassurotni ham beradi. Bu o'quvchilar har doim mashq qilishlari kerak bo'lgan jismoniy mahoratdir. Shunday qilib, darsda ko'rsatmalar va amaliyot kerak. Ushbu maqola talaffuzning ahamiyatini tahlil qiladi, inglizcha talaffuz va muloqotni muhokama qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Talaffuz, Inglizcha talaffuz, muloqot, talaffuzning ahamiyati,

noto'g'ri talaffuzning sababi.

Аннотация

Неотъемлемой частью изучения английского языка является правильное произношение. Если произношение учащегося плохое, это приводит к тому, что его не понимают другие, даже если его навыки грамматики, аудирования, письма и чтения идеальны. Произношение важно не только для того, чтобы вас поняли, но и для того, чтобы произвести первое впечатление о человеке. Это физический навык, который учащиеся должны практиковать каждый раз. Поэтому на занятиях необходимы инструкции и практика. В этой статье анализируется важность произношения, обсуждается английское произношение и общение.

Ключевые слова: Произношение, английское произношение, общение, важность произношения, причины неправильного произношения

Introduction

Process of exchanging information, ideas, thoughts, feelings and beliefs between individuals is called communication. It can occur through various means, including spoken or written language, nonverbal cues (such as body language and facial expressions), visual aids, and digital platforms. It is worth to say that in spoken communication, pronunciation is number one thing. Many students who are learning English as their second language are making a big mistake by not paying attention to their pronunciation. They think that pronunciation is not more important than other aspects of the English language such as grammar, lexicology, and vocabulary. Communication is a mutual relationship between the speaker and the hearer. This means that one must comprehend what he/she hears in the target language and must produce the sounds of the language he/she is trying to learn accurately. Unless he has sufficient knowledge of the sound patterns of the target language, he can neither encode a message to anybody nor decode the message sent by another person by learning the sounds of the target language within his mother tongue. Therefore, pronunciation instruction is of great importance for

successful oral communication to take place since it is an important ingredient of the communicative

1. Importance of pronunciation

In order to express our ideas accurately in English, we have to work on our pronunciation more. It is an essential part of every speaker to speak with the right pronunciation. But many people underestimate this and they focus on their grammar and vocabulary. They think that with two of them they can have a great communication with others in English language. But the fact is that pronunciation is extremely important. In many cases of misunderstanding in communication are caused by the mispronouncing of words or the improper intonation. For example if somebody pronounces the words big ['big] and pig [pig], write [rait] and ride ['raid], with relatively no differences, in some cases lead to misunderstanding. Another example: when one pronounces the word present with stress in the first syllable, whereas she uses in the sentence "I'd like to present" is certainly incorrect and irritating. In addition, good pronunciation can also give a plus value to those who master it. People get amazed of your English language when they hear you speaking in English and thinking about your pronunciation skill? The answer is the quality of the pronunciation. Good pronunciation skill can give you more self-confidence when you speak in front of many people.

2. Reason for incorrect pronunciation

There are two main reasons which can lead us to incorrect pronunciation. In a native or first language situation, from a very early stage children learn to respond to sounds and tones which their elders habitually use while talking to them. In due course, children start learning English in English speaking countries; they tend to speak in the mother tongue accent. But in our country, where English is used as second language, children listen to wrong sounds and tones spoken by their teachers/grownups in their environment and tend to pick up faulty pronunciation. This happens mainly due to their lack of sufficient exposure to the right variety of the language. Moreover, we tend to speak English as we speak our mother tongue;

therefore we tend to commit mistakes due to its influence.

3. Conclusion

Good pronunciation skill can give you more self – confidence when you speak in front of many people. English pronunciation involves to many complexities for learners to strive for a complete elimination of accent, but improving pronunciation will boost self esteem, facilitate communication and possibly lead to a better job or at least, more respect in the workplace among people. This leads to the conclusion that speech should be emphasized accurately for the effective communication.

4. Used materials

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